

ISic2752

I.Sicily inscription 2752

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di San Giovanni

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1994

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645155

PHI 332971

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 44.0794

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Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia

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